

QbD-based optimization of wet milling for the synthesis of glimepiride-metformin HCl nano-cocrystal suspension using various stabilizers

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Abstract

Glimepiride (GLI) and metformin HCl (MET) are widely co-administered as oral antidiabetic agents for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). From a crystal engineering perspective, this combination can be developed into a multidrug cocrystal (CC) to improve physicochemical properties. With appropriate stabilizers, the CC can be further processed into a nano-cocrystal (NCC), potentially enhancing physicochemical properties, which in turn improve oral bioavailability and facilitate better manufacturability. The main objective of this research was the screening of cocrystal formation to produce GLI–MET CC powder, which was further synthesized into GLI–MET NCC. This process began with a Box–Behnken design (BBD) to optimize formulation variables for NCC suspension preparation using various stabilizers such as poloxamer 188 (P188), poloxamer 407 (P407), Tween 80 (T80), and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) by a top-down wet milling method using Quality by Design (QbD) principles. The GLI–MET CC, prepared via solvent evaporation at an equimolar ratio, showed improved solubility and dissolution of GLI. It was further processed into an NCC suspension using a dual stabilizer combination of P188 (0.2% w/v) and T80 (1.0% w/v), identified as the optimal formulation by wet milling with a reciprocating ball mill. Milling was conducted with three balls at 350 rpm for 30 min. The resulting NCC suspension exhibited a particle size of 452.6 ± 7.8 nm, a polydispersity index of 0.482 ± 0.012 , and a zeta potential of -31.30 ± 0.26 mV. The formulation demonstrated good stability over 3 months at room temperature.

Keywords

cocrystal, glimepiride, metformin HCl, nano-cocrystal, nanosuspension, wet milling

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization, by 2030, the number of people with diabetes mellitus worldwide is projected to reach approximately 366 million, with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) having the highest prevalence among these cases (Guzman-Vilca and Carrillo-Larco

2024). According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), the countries with the highest number of T2DM cases globally are India, China, the United States, Pakistan, and Indonesia (Yu et al. 2021). Therapy for T2DM generally requires a combination of oral antidiabetic drugs. A commonly used combination is the third-generation sulfonylurea class, namely GLI, as a long-term

treatment, with the biguanide class, namely MET, as the first-choice treatment. This combination provides complementary and synergistic effects with dual targets: improving insulin secretion and enhancing insulin action in tissues (Maruthur et al. 2016).

However, both GLI and MET have several limitations in their physicochemical properties. GLI has poor dissolution (BCS Class II) (Ammar et al. 2006), while MET has high solubility (BCS Class III) but is highly hygroscopic. Therefore, it is generally available in the hydrochloride salt form to overcome the high hygroscopicity of its base form (Ammar et al. 2006; Li et al. 2007). In addition, MET has low permeability, resulting in only about 50–60% oral absorption (Hariharan et al. 1989; Childs et al. 2004; Li et al. 2007).

Many methods have been adopted to address physicochemical limitations of drugs, one of which is cocrystallization. Cocrystallization involves combining active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) that act as hosts with cocrystal-forming substances or cofomers that act as guests, interacting through noncovalent bonds within the same crystal lattice (Trask and Jones 2005). This interaction can yield multidrug crystals that combine APIs with other APIs having synergistic pharmacological effects (Thipparaboina et al. 2016). Multidrug crystals can not only modify physicochemical properties such as dissolution rate, hygroscopicity, and stability—which affect bioavailability—but also improve pharmacological performance (Remenar et al. 2003; Almarsson and Zaworotko 2004; Childs et al. 2004; Paufler 2012).

A cocrystal (CC) with nanometer dimensions is referred to as a nano-cocrystal (NCC), which can offer the combined advantages of both cocrystals and nanocrystals. One of the main benefits is a significant enhancement in oral bioavailability due to a rapid dissolution rate, which results from increased solubility and the larger surface area of nanosized drug particles (Karashima et al. 2016). NCCs are generally prepared using two main approaches: a top-down technique such as wet milling, which uses shear forces to reduce particle size from micrometer to nanometer dimensions (Merisko-Liversidge et al. 2003, 2011; Witika et al. 2021), or a bottom-up approach such as sonication–precipitation, where crystal growth is inhibited by using suitable stabilizers to maintain nanometer dimensions (De Waard et al. 2011; Sinha et al. 2013; Witika et al. 2020). Both techniques typically involve the use of polymers or surfactants as stabilizers, which act through mechanisms of steric hindrance and/or electrostatic repulsion.

In this study, the process began with screening GLI–MET CC formation at an equimolar ratio using various techniques to obtain GLI–MET CC powder. This powder was subsequently prepared into a GLI–MET NCC suspension using a top-down approach via the wet milling–reciprocating ball mill method. This technique employs milling balls that move linearly back and forth within a narrow chamber matching the diameter of the ball mill. It is adapted from nano wet media milling, where the crystals of the API collide with the milling media, other API particles, and the walls of the milling chamber (Merisko-Liversidge

et al. 2004; Witika et al. 2021). Most of the forces responsible for particle reduction in media milling are due to API particle–bead interactions, with particle–particle interactions making a minor contribution (Witika et al. 2021). In contrast, methods such as jet milling and high-pressure homogenization (HPH) involve significant contributions from both particle–particle and particle–wall interactions in achieving particle size reduction (Brosh et al. 2014).

The manufacture of NCC using wet milling methods has been successfully achieved (De Smet et al. 2014; Karashima et al. 2016; Huang et al. 2022). An itraconazole–adipic acid NCC suspension with a particle diameter of 549 nm was prepared by wet milling a physical mixture of itraconazole and adipic acid with 1.25% (w/v) Tween 80. The dissolution and oral absorption of the NCC were equivalent to or greater than those observed for the amorphous formulation (De Smet et al. 2014). Monodisperse carbamazepine–saccharin, indomethacin–saccharin, and furosemide–caffeine nanocrystal suspensions, as well as a furosemide–cytosine nano-salt suspension, were successfully prepared with particle sizes below 300 nm by wet milling using hydroxypropyl methylcellulose and sodium dodecyl sulfate at 0.5% and 0.02% (w/v), respectively (Karashima et al. 2016). Nano-cocrystals of itraconazole–fumaric acid, itraconazole–succinic acid, indomethacin–saccharin, and indomethacin–nicotinamide, with particle sizes ranging from 300 to 450 nm and a stable physical solid state, were prepared by wet milling using 1.0% (w/v) poloxamer 407 as a stabilizer (Huang et al. 2022).

A Design of Experiments (DoE) approach, specifically a Box–Behnken Design (BBD) supported by Response Surface Methodology (RSM), was used to optimize formulation variables for the manufacture of GLI–MET NCC suspension using wet milling with a reciprocating ball mill. A factorial design involving four factors at three levels was employed to optimize the key characteristics influencing the response variables. The critical material attributes (CMAs) considered in this study were stabilizer concentration, number of balls, milling time, and milling speed. These attributes were evaluated at three levels: low, medium, and high. The critical quality attributes (CQAs) evaluated included particle size (PS), polydispersity index (PDI), and zeta potential (ZP) (Dewi et al. 2024).

The novelty of this research lies in the development of GLI–MET CC, which was further formulated into NCC. The process began with optimizing the GLI–MET NCC suspension using various stabilizers through wet milling with a reciprocating ball mill, guided by Quality by Design (QbD) principles and employing a Box–Behnken Design (BBD). The preparation of both CC and NCC aimed to significantly enhance the solubility, dissolution rate, and stability of the drug, thereby improving its oral bioavailability (Li et al. 2016; Pi et al. 2019).

The main objective of this research was the screening of cocrystal formation to produce GLI–MET CC powder, which was further developed into a GLI–MET NCC suspension. This process began with a BBD to optimize formulation variables for NCC suspension

preparation using various stabilizers through wet milling with a reciprocating ball mill guided by QbD principles. The candidate stabilizers selected were poloxamer 188 (P188) (Pi et al. 2019), poloxamer 407 (P407) (Huang et al. 2022), Tween 80 (T80) (De Smet et al. 2014), and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) (Karashima et al. 2016; Huang et al. 2022). Evaluations were carried out using dynamic light scattering (DLS). Finally, stability testing of the optimized NCC suspension was conducted to complete the study, emphasizing the importance of nanosizing in formulation performance.

Materials and methods

Materials

GLI was purchased from PT Kimia Farma Tbk (Indonesia), derived from Glenmark (India; batch no. 0000116238), and MET was purchased from PT Meprofarm (Indonesia), derived from Sohan Healthcare (India; batch no. H09700922-23). Both were used as the active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). P188, P407, T80 for synthesis, and SDS for synthesis were purchased from Merck (Germany) and used as stabilizer candidates.

The reagents used included methanol, disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4), and potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4), all purchased from Merck (Germany). Water for injection (WFI), purchased from IPHA Laboratories (Bandung, Indonesia), was used as the solvent for stabilizers and for DLS measurements.

Instruments

An in-house reciprocating ball mill with a wet milling chamber made of stainless steel was used as the actuator and reactor, respectively. Stainless steel balls (316L type) with a diameter of 14.975 ± 0.05 mm and a weight of 13.835 ± 0.007 g were used as the milling media.

Methods

Preparation of GLI–MET cocrystal

1. Physical mixtures (PM)

Equimolar amounts of GLI (1.9625 g; 0.004 mol) and MET (0.6625 g; 0.004 mol) were accurately weighed using an analytical balance (Mettler Toledo ME204, Switzerland) and mixed manually with a spatula in a glass vial.

2. Neat grinding (NG)

Equimolar amounts of GLI (1.9625 g; 0.004 mol) and MET (0.6625 g; 0.004 mol) were accurately weighed using an analytical balance (Mettler Toledo ME204, Switzerland) and manually ground using a mortar and pestle for 30 min.

3. Solvent drop grinding (SDG)

Equimolar amounts of GLI (1.9625 g; 0.004 mol) and MET (0.6625 g; 0.004 mol) were accurately weighed using an analytical balance (Mettler Toledo ME204, Switzerland) and manually ground using a mortar and pestle for 30 min. During grinding, small amounts of methanol were added dropwise (approximately 10 drops every 10 min).

4. Solvent evaporation (SE)

Equimolar amounts of GLI (981.234 mg; 2 mmol) and MET (331.26 mg; 2 mmol) were accurately weighed using an analytical balance (Mettler Toledo ME204, Switzerland). GLI was dissolved in 500 mL of warm methanol (50 ± 5 °C) and stirred using a hot-plate magnetic stirrer (IKA C-MAG HS7, Germany) at 200 rpm for 30 min until clear. MET was dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water at room temperature under stirring at 750 rpm for 15 min. The MET solution was added dropwise to the GLI solution using a 10 mL syringe, then stirred at 50 ± 5 °C and 200 rpm for 60 min until homogeneous. The mixture was left to cocrystallize at room temperature for 72 h, followed by recrystallization via slow evaporation in a dehydrator at 30 °C for 48 h.

Characterization of GLI–MET cocrystal

1. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

Approximately 5–10 mg of each sample was dispersed with potassium bromide (KBr) powder using a crystal mortar and pestle, then compressed into a pellet. The spectra were recorded in the wavenumber range of $4000\text{--}400$ cm^{-1} with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . Measurements were performed in triplicate ($n = 3$) using an IRPrestige-21 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) equipped with IRsolution software.

2. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Thermal characteristics were studied using a DSC 214 Polyma (NETZSCH, Germany), and the data generated were analyzed using NETZSCH Proteus software. Accurately weighed samples (3–5 mg) were placed into aluminum pans, crimped, and heated at a scanning rate of 10 °C per minute over a temperature range of 30 °C to 300 °C under nitrogen. All DSC analyses were conducted in triplicate ($n = 3$) under a nitrogen atmosphere purged at a flow rate of 40 mL/min.

3. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD)

X-ray powder diffraction data were collected using a Rigaku Miniflex 600 (Japan) equipped with a proportional counter, Cu-K α radiation ($K\alpha_1 = 1.54060$ nm; $K\alpha_2 = 1.54439$ nm), and a nickel filter. Samples (100–200 mg) were placed on a sample holder and measured at a generator setting of 40 kV and a current of 15 mA. Data were collected in triplicate in the 2θ range of $5^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$ at a scanning rate of 10° per minute.

4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

A scanning electron microscope (Hitachi TM3000, Japan) was used to visualize the morphology and crystal habit of the samples at various magnifications. Approximately 1–2 mg of each sample was dusted onto double-sided carbon tape attached to a sample holder, placed in the sample chamber, and irradiated at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV ($n = 3$).

5. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX)

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS; JEOL JSM-6510LA, Japan) was used for elemental analysis to identify the chemical elements of the CC and reference materials. Approximately 1 mg of each sample was dusted onto a graphite plate and irradiated at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV ($n = 3$).

Performance evaluation of GLI–MET cocrystal

1. Determination of micromeritic properties

Flow properties analysis entails the utilization of a flow tester to measure the flow rate and determine the angle of repose. The flow rate is calculated by dividing the mass of the compacted material (100 grams) by the time it takes to pass through a funnel (g/s). An optimal flow rate is indicated when the time required for the flow of 100 grams is less than 10 s.

The angle of repose was determined by measuring the angle formed between the slope of the flowing powder heap from the funnel and a flat surface. The angle of repose was interpreted as follows: $\alpha = 25^\circ$ – 30° indicates very easy flow, $\alpha = 30^\circ$ – 38° signifies easy flow, and $\alpha > 38^\circ$ denotes poor flow.

The compressibility percentage indicates the ability of the compacted mass to be compressed into tablet dosage forms. A lower compressibility percentage suggests excellent flow properties of the compacted mass. Determination of the compressibility percentage began with the measurement of bulk density, including bulk density before compression and bulk density after compression, using a tap densitometer. The bulk density before compression was determined by measuring the volume of a 50 g sample poured into a 250 mL measuring cylinder without tapping and recording the volume. In contrast, the bulk density after compression was measured using the same method as the bulk density before compression but with 10 and 500 taps applied.

The compressibility percentage of the powder was determined based on the measurements of bulk density before and after compression using the following equation.

$$\%C = \frac{\text{Tapped Bulk Density} - \text{Bulk Density}}{\text{Tapped Bulk Density}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Interpretation of the results was as follows: $\%C = 5$ – 15% indicates excellent flow, $\%C = 16$ – 25% signifies good flow, and $\%C \geq 26\%$ represents poor flow.

2. Solubility study

The solubility test was conducted by weighing an excess amount of powder equivalent to 5 mg of GLI (6.6879 mg of each powder: PM, NG, SDG, and SE) and placing it into a 20 mL vial. Each vial was filled with 20 mL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) and placed in a shaker water bath (Labtech LSB 045S, South Korea) at 150 rpm and $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The mixtures were stirred for 24 h to reach equilibrium.

Afterward, the samples were filtered using Whatman filter paper, and the absorbance was measured using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 200–300 nm. The first derivative absorbance of GLI in the samples was obtained using OriginPro® software (Savitzky–Golay smoothing; polynomial order = 6; points of window = 20). The GLI concentration in each sample was determined by inserting the first derivative absorbance value of GLI at 233 nm into the first derivative calibration curve equation for GLI. All samples were measured in triplicate.

3. Drug release study

Drug release studies were conducted by determining the dissolution rate of the particles. A powder equivalent to 10 mg of GLI (13.3760 mg of each sample: PM, NG, SDG, and SE) was accurately weighed, and each sample was placed into the vessel of a type II (paddle) dissolution apparatus (Varian–Agilent 708-DS, USA) containing 900 mL of PBS (pH 7.4) maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred at 75 rpm. Aliquots of 10 mL were withdrawn at time intervals of 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 min. An equal volume (10 mL) of fresh dissolution medium at the same temperature was replaced after each sampling.

Each aliquot was filtered using Whatman filter paper, and the absorbance was measured using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 200–300 nm. The first derivative absorbance values of GLI in the samples were processed using OriginPro® software with the Savitzky–Golay smoothing function (polynomial order = 6; points of window = 20). The GLI concentration in each sample was determined by inserting the first derivative absorbance value of GLI at 233 nm into the first derivative calibration curve equation for GLI. All samples were measured in triplicate.

Preparation of GLI–MET nano-cocrystal suspension

The NCC suspension was manufactured using a top-down approach, specifically through wet milling with a reciprocating ball mill and a wet milling chamber (in-house instrument) serving as the actuator and reactor, respectively. The process consisted of a pre-optimization stage to select stabilizer candidates (P188, P407, T80, and SDS) and an optimization stage to determine the optimal formulation for the selected stabilizer based on the responses of particle size (PS), polydispersity index (PDI), and zeta potential (ZP) in Box–Behnken Design (BBD) experiments.

1. Selection of stabilizer candidate

An aliquot of 10 mg of harvested or dried CC was accurately weighed using a Mettler Toledo ME204 electronic balance (Greifensee, Switzerland) and placed in a milling chamber. Subsequently, 1.0 mL of 0.4% (w/v) P188 solution was added using a micropipette. Milling was performed with three balls in a reciprocating ball mill for 10 min at a speed of 300 rpm until an NCC suspension was formed, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Selection of stabilizer candidate.

Factor	Stabilizer			
	P188	P407	T80	SDS
Concentration (% w/v)	0.4	1.0	2.0	0.4
Number of balls	3	3	3	3
Milling time (min)	10	10	10	10
Milling speed (rpm)	300	300	300	300

The NCC suspension sample was transferred into a 1.5 mL microtube and evaluated for PS, PDI, and ZP. The same procedure was applied to other stabilizer solutions—1.0% (w/v) P407, 2.0% (w/v) T80, and 0.4% (w/v) SDS. All samples were prepared in triplicate.

2. Development of NCC suspension formulation prediction using BBD

A factorial design involving four factors at three levels was employed to optimize the essential characteristics influencing the response variables. The critical material attributes (CMAs) considered in this study were the concentration of stabilizer (A), number of balls (B), milling time (C), and milling speed (D). These attributes were evaluated at three levels: low, medium, and high. The critical quality attributes (CQAs) evaluated included PS (Y_1), PDI (Y_2), and ZP (Y_3).

A BBD generated using Design Expert® software version 13 (Stat-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, Minnesota, USA) was employed to optimize formulation variables and process parameters for NCC suspension production via wet milling with a reciprocating ball mill.

The most appropriate model for each measured response was selected based on the predicted and adjusted coefficients of determination. Adequate precision was also calculated to ensure model fit. The equation representing the model with the best fit was derived. The statistical technique of analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess the significance of the investigated variables by analyzing the measured response, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$. Response surface analysis and contour plots, as well as 3D response surface plots, were generated to illustrate the relationships and interactions between variables (Dewi et al 2024).

3. Optimization of NCC suspension using various stabilizers by BBD

An aliquot of 10 mg of harvested or dried CC was accurately weighed using a Mettler Toledo ME204 electronic

balance (Greifensee, Switzerland) and placed in the milling chamber. Subsequently, 1.0 mL of P188 solution at various % (w/v) concentrations, as defined by the BBD, was added to the chamber. Milling was conducted using a reciprocating ball mill until an NCC suspension was formed, with the number of balls, milling time, and milling speed set according to the BBD parameters.

The resulting NCC suspension was transferred into a 1.5 mL microtube and evaluated for PS, PDI, and ZP. The same procedure was applied to other stabilizer solutions, namely P407 and T80, whereas SDS was not continued. A total of 30 runs were performed for each stabilizer, as summarized in Table 2.

Formulation optimization

The optimal formulation, determined through numerical optimization, was obtained by processing the factors and responses from the BBD experiment using Design Expert® software version 13 (Stat-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, Minnesota, USA). This approach was used to identify the formulation and process parameters that would yield a critical quality attribute (CQA) suitable for producing an NCC suspension with optimal stability.

Dynamic light scattering

The ZP, PDI, and PS were measured using a Zetasizer Nano ZSP (Malvern Instruments, Worcestershire, United Kingdom). An aliquot of 100 μ L of the NCC suspension was diluted with 10 mL of WFI and transferred to a disposable polystyrene cuvette (DTS0012) for PS and PDI determination and to a disposable folded polystyrene capillary cell (DTS1070) for ZP measurement.

Stability studies

The stability of the GLI–MET NCC suspension was evaluated under two storage conditions. Room-temperature stability studies were conducted at 25 ± 2 °C and $60 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity, while accelerated stability studies were performed at 40 ± 2 °C and $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity. Samples were collected at 30, 60, and 90 days. PS, PDI, and ZP were measured using DLS to compare the stability profiles of the NCC suspension with single stabilizers and without stabilizers.

Results and discussion

Prediction of supramolecular synthons for the cocrystal formation between GLI and MET

In this study, the formation of the GLI–MET CC was carried out using metformin HCl. This differs from that reported by Bian (2019), who used a metformin base. In our previous study, the physical interaction between GLI and metformin HCl (Fig. 1) was identified at various compositions based on their molecular ratios. These binary mix-

Table 2. Summary of the BBD experimental runs, independent and dependent variables for NCC suspension preparation with P188, P407, and T80.

Run (formulation code)	Values of independent variables											
	Conc. of stabilizer (A)			Number of balls (B)			Milling time (C)			Milling speed (D)		
	P188	P407	T80	P188	P407	T80	P188	P407	T80	P188	P407	T80
1	0.2	0.5	1	2	2	3	20	10	20	250	300	300
2	0.2	1	2	2	2	3	10	30	30	300	350	300
3	0.2	1	2	2	2	2	20	20	30	350	300	250
4	0.4	1	2	2	3	3	20	10	20	300	300	350
5	0.4	1	2	3	3	2	10	30	20	300	300	300
6	0.4	1	3	1	1	2	10	30	10	300	300	300
7	0.4	1.5	2	3	3	3	20	20	10	250	300	300
8	0.4	0.5	2	1	2	2	20	20	10	250	250	250
9	0.6	1	2	1	1	2	20	20	20	300	350	300
10	0.4	0.5	2	2	2	1	30	30	20	250	300	250
11	0.4	1	1	2	2	2	10	10	20	250	350	350
12	0.6	1	1	3	2	2	20	20	30	300	300	300
13	0.4	1	3	1	2	2	30	30	30	300	250	300
14	0.4	1.5	2	2	2	1	20	30	20	300	300	350
15	0.6	1	2	2	3	2	20	20	20	250	350	300
16	0.4	1.5	2	2	2	2	30	10	30	350	300	350
17	0.4	1	3	3	2	2	30	10	20	300	250	250
18	0.4	1.5	3	2	2	1	20	20	20	300	350	300
19	0.4	0.5	3	2	3	3	20	20	20	300	300	300
20	0.4	1.5	1	3	2	1	20	20	20	350	250	300
21	0.6	1	1	2	1	2	20	10	10	350	300	300
22	0.4	1	2	2	2	2	20	20	10	300	300	350
23	0.6	0.5	2	2	2	1	10	20	10	300	350	300
24	0.2	1	2	3	1	2	20	20	20	300	250	300
25	0.2	1	2	2	2	3	30	20	20	300	300	250
26	0.4	0.5	2	2	1	1	20	20	30	300	300	300
27	0.4	1	2	1	2	2	20	20	20	350	300	300
28	0.4	1	2	2	2	2	10	20	20	350	300	300
29	0.6	1	3	2	3	2	30	20	20	300	250	350
30	0.2	1.5	1	1	1	2	20	20	20	300	300	250

Independent variable	Level		
	Low (-1)	Medium (0)	High (+1)
A: Concentration of stabilizer (% w/v):			
- P188	0.2	0.4	0.6
- P407	0.5	1.0	1.5
- T80	1.0	2.0	3.0
B: Number of balls	1	2	3
C: Milling time (min)	10	20	30
D: Milling speed (rpm)	250	300	350

Dependent variables	Criteria
Y ₁ : Particle size	<1000 nm
Y ₂ : Polydispersity index	<0.5
Y ₃ : Zeta potential	>+30 or <-30 mV

Figure 1. The two-dimensional structures of **a.** GLI and **b.** MET generated using Chemdraw® software.

tures were thermally analyzed using DSC to obtain the melting point from the endothermic peak of the DSC thermogram, which was then used to construct a phase diagram of the binary system. The results showed a congruent pattern, indicating the formation of a cocrystal or molecular compound at a 1:1 molar ratio (Darusman et al. 2021).

The results were further confirmed through a computational approach using molecular docking simulations and molecular dynamics. These computational methods have proven capable of identifying and confirming the physical interaction between GLI and MET. Fig. 2 shows that the interaction between GLI and MET did not result in the

Figure 2. The three-dimensional (a) and two-dimensional (b) interactions of GLI and MET in docking simulations (Darusman et al. 2021).

formation of new compounds. Instead, the interaction involves the formation of hydrogen bonds with heterosynthion formation (Table 3), along with minimal van der Waals interactions, with a total energy of -0.00096 \AA and a binding-free energy value of -415.35 kJ/mol . The negative free binding energy indicates that the physical interaction between GLI and MET occurs spontaneously (Hu et al. 2017; Darusman et al. 2021). These findings demonstrate the presence of cocrystal interactions (molecular compound) between GLI and metformin HCl at a 1:1 molar ratio.

Ultimately, the formation of the GLI–MET CC oc-

Table 3. Interaction between GLI and MET from docking simulations (Darusman et al. 2021).

GLI atom	MET atom	Distance of interaction (Å)	Type of interaction
Oxygen (O ₂)	Hydrogen (H11)	2.98128	Hydrogen bond
Oxygen (O ₂)	Hydrogen (H13)	1.89064	Hydrogen bond

curred at an equimolar ratio of 1:1, despite the fact that the therapeutic doses of the two drugs differ significantly (GLI: 1–4 mg; MET: 500 mg). In the development of the final dosage form—such as tablets—a series of preclinical and clinical studies will be required to determine whether dosage adjustments are necessary. However, based on cocrystal formation theory, particularly for multidrug cocrystals where a molecular compound is formed from multiple APIs, there is a potential for dose reduction, especially for MET. This may help minimize associated side effects (Almarsson and Zaworotko 2004).

Characterization results of GLI–MET cocrystal

1. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

FTIR spectral analysis was used to detect differences between GLI, MET, and GLI–MET CC at the molecular level. In principle, the IR spectrum of GLI–MET should represent a superposition of the IR spectra of its pure components, with slight shifts observed in the functional groups involved in strong hydrogen bonding or increased intensity. Additionally, the removal of a hydrogen atom

from the amino group of GLI renders the nitrogen anionic. This can enhance conjugation effects, causing the absorption of surrounding groups to shift, leading to peaks at higher frequencies or changes in intensity—indicating the strength and nature of hydrogen bonding in the formed CC. This phenomenon occurred during the formation of the GLI–MET CC, as shown in Fig. 3.

Based on Suppl. material 1: table S1, in the SE, the N–H vibration (3371 cm^{-1}) of MET experienced a frequency

Figure 3. IR-spectrum overlay of powder: GLI (a), MET (b), PM (c), NG (d), SDG (e), SE (f).

shift (3369 cm^{-1}) and an increase in peak intensity (%T) from 40 to 5. This was influenced by the hydrogen atom from the nitrogen between the sulfonyl and carbamide groups of GLI moving to the biguanide bond of MET. The C=O vibrations of the sulfonyl and lactam groups (1708 cm^{-1} and 1675 cm^{-1}) of GLI shifted to lower frequencies, showing new absorption peaks (1706 cm^{-1} and 1673 cm^{-1}), which were affected by the appearance of electron pairs due to the formation of N anions.

2. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC thermal analysis is an analytical technique used for thermal characterization of interactions between two or more solid-state drug materials (solid-state interactions).

It evaluates changes in thermodynamic properties when a solid drug is subjected to heat energy, as indicated by recrystallization, polymorphic transitions, melting, desolvation, or dehydration—events that appear as endothermic or exothermic peaks on the DSC thermogram (Almarsson and Zaworotko 2004). The DSC thermograms display endothermic peak data corresponding to the melting points and enthalpy values of all samples, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. DSC thermogram overlay of powder: GLI (a), MET (b), PM (c), NG (d), SDG (e), SE (f).

The DSC thermogram revealed that GLI melted endothermically at 201.2 °C with an enthalpy of 126.68 J/g, while MET exhibited an endothermic melting peak at 234.9 °C with an enthalpy of 415.41 J/g. The PM showed two endothermic peaks, each displaying a slight decrease in melting point compared with those of the single components—GLI at 190.9 °C (enthalpy 5.30 J/g) and MET at 223.4 °C (enthalpy 184.88 J/g). The SDG showed two endothermic peaks: peak 1 at 193.3 °C and peak 2 (pseudo peak) at 217.2 °C with an enthalpy of 300.71 J/g.

In contrast, NG and SE each showed one distinct endothermic peak at 191.3 °C (enthalpy 167.66 J/g) and 193.2 °C (enthalpy 168.16 J/g), respectively. Although NG and SE exhibited similar peak profiles, the enthalpy of SE was slightly higher than that of NG. Enthalpy represents the heat energy absorbed or released by a sample during a thermal event. In the melting process, melting enthalpy indicates the amount of energy absorbed (endothermic) to melt a crystal. A high enthalpy value reflects greater crystal stability. Screening of GLI–MET CC formation suggests that crystallization likely occurred in the SE technique, which produced a new crystalline phase or cocrystal at 193.2 °C with an enthalpy of 168.16 J/g (Qiao et al. 2011).

3. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD)

PXRD analysis is a primary method for determining internal crystal structure and evaluating structural arrangements, phase transitions, crystallinity, and preferential orientation in solid materials (Zhang et al. 2004). In cocrystal formation,

PXRD is used to characterize the diffraction pattern resulting from the interaction between the API and the cofomer, indicated by a diffraction pattern distinct from that of the physical mixture (Childs et al. 2004). These differences are typically observed as changes in peak position, sharpness, or broadening, which may also be influenced by preferential orientation effects. Preferential orientation occurs when the crystals within a solid sample are not randomly oriented but tend to align in a specific direction. Crystals with anisotropic morphology exhibit stronger preferential orientation effects than isotropic crystals (Hinrichsen and Dinnebier 2013).

Fig. 5 shows that GLI and MET exhibit sharp and intense diffraction peaks, primarily due to the anisotropic crystal morphology of both compounds. This anisotropy causes certain crystal planes to dominate the diffraction pattern, resulting in strong preferential orientation effects. Data from five high-intensity interference peaks in the PXRD diffractograms of GLI and MET are presented in Suppl. material 1: table S2.

Figure 5. PXRD diffractogram overlay of powder: GLI (a), MET (b), PM (c), NG (d), SDG (e), SE (f).

According to Suppl. material 1: table S3, the diffractogram of PM displayed a combination of the interference peaks of GLI and MET, with reduced intensities and without any new peaks. The peaks at 2θ values of 6.30°, 13.40°, and 21.02° were identified as characteristic of GLI, whereas those at 2θ 17.55° and 21.21° corresponded to characteristic peaks of MET. The diffraction pattern of the PM thus represents a combination of the two anisotropic forms of GLI and MET, in which the preferential orientation effect is likely still pronounced.

In contrast, the samples obtained from cocrystallization using various techniques (NG, SDG, and SE) exhibited broader peaks with lower intensities. This behavior is associated with a more isotropic and irregular particle morphology, resulting in a more uniform diffraction pattern with reduced preferential orientation effects.

Specifically, in the SE diffractogram, the characteristic peaks of GLI and MET were absent; however, two new peaks with low intensities were detected at $2\theta = 18.88^\circ$ (peak intensity 414) and 20.97° (peak intensity 670). These peaks

may indicate the presence of a minor crystalline phase, possibly arising from anisotropic crystal morphology formed during the solvent evaporation process, which led to preferential orientation effects (Hinrichsen and Dinnebiec 2013). Therefore, this diffractogram result requires further confirmation through complementary characterization using FTIR, DSC, SEM, and EDX analyses.

4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

SEM analysis was used to determine the surface morphology of the solids. This characterization helps to

observe the surface topography, grain size, and crystal habit of the materials. The results of SEM analysis of GLI, MET, the PM of GLI–MET, and the cocrystallization products obtained by various techniques (NG, SDG, and SE) are shown in Fig. 6.

In the SEM micrographs, GLI crystals (5.0–20 μm) appeared as irregular particles forming aggregates, whereas MET crystals (10–60 μm) were observed as spherical particles with relatively uniform sizes. In the PM image, MET particles (approximately 50 μm in diameter) with smooth surfaces were surrounded by dispersed GLI particles ($\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$), appearing in a matrix-like

Figure 6. SEM micrographs of powder: GLI (a), MET (b), PM (c), NG (d), SDG (e), SE (f) at 1000 \times magnification.

arrangement. The NG and SDG images did not show significant differences compared with PM. However, in NG, GLI particles ($\pm 3 \mu\text{m}$) appeared more homogeneous and did not form aggregates, while MET particles ($\pm 30 \mu\text{m}$) were smaller than before, which can be attributed to the milling process. In SDG, the surfaces of MET particles ($\pm 40 \mu\text{m}$) appeared to be coated with GLI particles ($\pm 4 \mu\text{m}$), resulting from the milling process in the presence of solvent droplets. In contrast, the SE image exhibited rod- or cylinder-shaped crystals, distinct from the other forms. This crystal habit indicates the formation of a new crystalline phase, namely the cocrystal.

5. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX)

EDX spectroscopy, also referred to as energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), is based on the generation of X-rays following the interaction of an electron beam with atoms in a sample. Apart from a continuous spectrum of X-rays produced by deceleration of beam electrons due to atomic interactions, sharp X-ray signals are generated at wavelengths specific to each element. These signals form the basis for elemental mapping by SEM–EDX (Ebnesajjad 2011; Müllertz et al. 2016; Witika et al. 2020).

EDX spectroscopy was employed to perform elemental analysis of the CC powder as a simple confirmation of successful CC formation. The analysis was conducted on the CC solid obtained from the best screening result (SE), identified as the optimal CC based on FTIR, DSC, PXRD, and SEM characterization, and was compared with the pure drugs.

Elemental analysis by EDX revealed the presence of carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, and sulfur in GLI (molecular formula: $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{S}$). In MET (molecular formula: $\text{C}_4\text{H}_{12}\text{ClN}_5$), the detected elements were carbon, nitrogen, and chlorine. The EDX data for PM demonstrated a combined elemental composition corresponding to both GLI and MET.

Based on Table 4, Suppl. material 1: fig. S1, the CC (SE) exhibited the same elemental composition as the PM—namely carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, sulfur, and chlorine—with slight differences in the percentage of atomic composition. These differences are presumed to arise from the non-covalent interactions formed within the CC, which influence the atomic percentage composition of each element in the GLI–MET CC (Witika et al. 2021). The presence of chlorine in the GLI–MET CC indicates the formation of a salt cocrystal between GLI and MET. This finding differs from the GLI–MET CC reported by Bian (2019).

Table 4. Summary of elemental analysis by EDX spectroscopy of GLI, MET, PM, and CC.

Element	Atomic %			
	GLI	MET	PM	CC (SE)
C	69.97 \pm 0.88	44.35 \pm 0.43	65.94 \pm 0.83	67.23 \pm 0.82
N	23.84 \pm 0.38	47.41 \pm 0.44	27.03 \pm 0.32	25.27 \pm 0.28
O	0.94 \pm 0.09	0	1.20 \pm 0.15	0.73 \pm 0.08
S	5.24 \pm 0.25	0	1.17 \pm 0.12	2.50 \pm 0.16
Cl	0	8.24 \pm 0.28	4.67 \pm 0.22	4.27 \pm 0.21

Performance evaluation results of GLI–MET cocrystal

The performance evaluation was conducted to identify the most effective technique for producing GLI–MET CC, particularly with regard to its physical and chemical performance. This evaluation included several parameters—flow properties, compressibility index, solubility, and drug release—which were compared with those of GLI and PM. The results presented in Table 5 show that the SE samples obtained through the solvent evaporation technique exhibited the most favorable physicochemical performance. In the screening of cocrystal formation using the solvent evaporation method, the dissolution of GLI and MET occurs at the molecular level, promoting the formation of additional hydrogen bonds. This is followed by the recrystallization process, during which rearrangement of GLI and MET molecules takes place. This rearrangement significantly improves the flow properties, compressibility index, solubility, and drug release of GLI (Giron 2001; Censi and Di Martino 2015).

The GLI sample exhibited very poor flow properties and a high compressibility index, as it could not flow freely. This is consistent with the characteristics of GLI, which exists as a fine, voluminous powder that tends to form agglomerates. In contrast, the MET sample displayed excellent flow properties and compressibility, consistent with its granular form. Table 5 shows that the SE sample successfully improved the flow properties and compressibility of GLI by forming a CC with MET, compared with NG and SDG.

Furthermore, solubility and drug release profiles were evaluated to assess the poor solubility of GLI, which is classified as a Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) Class II drug. As shown in Table 5, Suppl. material 1: figs S2, S3, the solubility of the SE sample was highest among all samples, including NG, SDG, GLI, and PM. In dissolution testing, the GLI release from the SE sample was consistently higher than that from the other samples over a 60 min period, reaching nearly 80%. This enhancement is attributed to hydrogen bond formation with MET.

The MET sample dissolved immediately upon contact with the medium, making it impossible to obtain solubility and drug release data. Therefore, no MET group was included in this test, confirming that MET is a highly soluble compound. In this context, the trends describing the physical and chemical performance of the samples were as follows: MET > SE > GLI/PM (Bian et al. 2019).

Preparation of GLI–MET nano-cocrystal suspensions

The GLI–MET NCC suspension was prepared using a top-down wet milling method with a reciprocating ball mill. One of the advantages of wet milling is that poorly water-soluble APIs can be readily modified to form nanosuspensions, which is a significant benefit. Furthermore, the process is easily scalable, with minimal batch-to-batch variability and a narrow size distribution of the

Table 5. The results of the evaluation.

Samples	Flow properties		Compressibility Index (%)	Solubility ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Drug release at 60 min (%)	Information
	Flow rate (g/s)	Angle of repose ($^\circ$)				
GLI	-	-	28.88 \pm 1.76	15.61 \pm 1.23	43.8 \pm 0.86	GLI (-) unable flow MET (-) uncalculated, directly soluble
MET	1.50 \pm 0.22	26.42 \pm 1.16	12.16 \pm 1.82	-	-	
PM	10.3 \pm 0.27	38.52 \pm 1.67	25.26 \pm 1.82	50.46 \pm 0.60	49.4 \pm 0.78	
NG	3.34 \pm 0.51	28.37 \pm 1.53	23.68 \pm 1.82	56.58 \pm 0.98	72.0 \pm 0.93	
SDG	3.10 \pm 0.75	33.82 \pm 1.67	26.24 \pm 1.38	54.89 \pm 0.24	71.8 \pm 0.78	
SE	1.20 \pm 0.12	25.42 \pm 1.16	14.55 \pm 1.55	61.35 \pm 0.76	78.7 \pm 0.78	
Criteria:						
Flow rate:	Angle of repose:		Compressibility index:			
≤ 10 g/s	$\alpha = 25^\circ\text{--}30^\circ \rightarrow$ very easy flow		%K = 5–15% \rightarrow very good flow			
	$\alpha = 30^\circ\text{--}38^\circ \rightarrow$ easy flow		%K = 16–25% \rightarrow good flow			
	$\alpha > 38^\circ \rightarrow$ poor flow		%K $\geq 26\%$ \rightarrow poor flow			

Description:

GLI = glimepiride pure;
 MET = metformin HCl pure;
 PM = physical mixture GLI–MET;
 NG = neat grinding GLI–MET;
 SDG = solvent drop grinding GLI–MET;
 SE = solvent evaporation GLI–MET.

final product (Merisko-Liversidge et al. 2004). During wet milling of an API, size reduction occurs when a coarse aqueous suspension containing dispersed micrometer-sized API crystals is milled with a solution of stabilizer(s) in the presence of hard beads as the milling medium. Mechanical attrition of the API particles occurs due to the milling media, resulting in a decrease in particle size. Typically, the extent of particle size reduction depends on the number of milling balls used and the speed or intensity of collisions between the API particles and the grinding media (Kwade 1999; Cerdeira et al. 2010).

Selected stabilizer

The manufacturing process of the GLI–MET NCC began with the formulation of a nanosuspension. Nanosuspensions are colloidal dispersions of insoluble APIs with particle sizes typically below 1000 nm, stabilized by surfactants or polymers to prevent aggregation (Chandra et al. 2013). Therefore, the selection of stabilizer candidates was conducted, including P188, P407, T80, and SDS.

In the formulation of nanosuspensions, the choice of an appropriate stabilizer is critical to ensuring physical stability and preventing nanoparticle aggregation. P188 contributes to stability by reducing interfacial tension between hydrophilic and lipophilic phases, enhancing particle dispersion, and providing steric stabilization through the formation of a protective layer around nanoparticles (Panda et al. 2018; Hou et al. 2023).

Similarly, P407, due to its amphiphilic structure, adsorbs onto the particle surface and offers steric hindrance, thereby minimizing surface energy and preventing particle agglomeration (Chen et al. 2022). P188 and P407 are ideal stabilizers for oral applications because of their high biocompatibility, excellent safety profiles, and low toxicity (McLain 2008; Kontogiannis et al. 2022).

T80, a nonionic surfactant, stabilizes nanosuspensions by lowering surface tension and forming a hydrophilic layer around the particles, which promotes uniform dispersion and reduces particle–particle interactions (Hanum et

al. 2023). T80 is a safe and compatible stabilizer commonly used in combination formulations to support NCC stabilization without increasing toxicity (Pawar et al. 2014).

In contrast, SDS, an anionic surfactant, imparts electrostatic stabilization by adsorbing onto particle surfaces and generating repulsive forces via negative surface charges. Despite its effectiveness, SDS exhibits higher toxicity than poloxamers. In oral NCC formulations, SDS as a stabilizer can open tight junctions in Caco-2 cells, enhancing permeability and bioavailability. However, its safety profile is inadequate for long-term oral use and requires strict dose evaluation (Liu et al. 2021). SDS is also frequently excluded from further formulation development because of concerns about its potential to induce particle growth under certain conditions (Huang et al. 2017).

The results of the pre-optimization study for NCC suspension formulation, aimed at selecting the most suitable stabilizer candidate, are presented in Table 6. The suspensions were prepared using a reciprocating ball mill with three balls for 10 min, following the method described by Witika et al. (2021), at a milling speed of 300 rpm, representing the medium-speed setting of the instrument. The concentration of each stabilizer candidate used in the formulations was based on their optimum concentrations reported in previous studies (De Smet et al. 2014; Karashima et al. 2016; Y. Huang et al. 2017; Pi et al. 2019; Huang et al. 2022). Based on the data shown in Table 6, the selected stabilizer candidates were P188, P407, and T80. The selection was primarily based on particle size values, with the requirement that particle size be less than 1000 nm. Because SDS did not meet this criterion, it was excluded from further optimization studies.

Table 6. Result of stabilizer candidate selection.

No	Stabilizer candidates	Concentration (%)	PS (nm)	PDI	ZP (mV)
1	P188	0.4	636.4 \pm 14.7	0.502 \pm 0.012	-34.7 \pm 0.5
2	P407	1.0	666.7 \pm 15.2	0.608 \pm 0.014	-25.6 \pm 0.3
3	T80	2.0	506.0 \pm 17.1	0.482 \pm 0.011	-25.0 \pm 0.2
4	SDS	0.4	1092 \pm 13.6	0.481 \pm 0.018	-47.9 \pm 0.6

Development of NCC suspension formulation prediction using BBD

Structurally, the NCC suspension is a nanosized colloidal dispersion in an aqueous phase, where key parameters such as particle size (PS), polydispersity index (PDI), and zeta potential (ZP) play a critical role in determining the formulation's stability and effectiveness. Therefore, it is essential to understand the influence of formulation variables—such as stabilizer concentration, number of milling balls, milling time, and milling speed (independent variables)—on PS, PDI, and ZP (dependent variables) for each selected stabilizer candidate, namely P188, P407, and T80. To investigate these effects, a BBD statistical approach was employed by designing 30 experimental batches for each stabilizer to systematically evaluate the impact of each independent variable on the selected formulation responses.

Optimization of NCC suspension using P188 by BBD

The results of NCC suspension formulation optimization using P188 as a stabilizer, along with both the experimental data (actual) and software-predicted responses, are presented in Suppl. material 1: table S4. Based on the experimental results, PS, PDI, and ZP ranged from 462.2 to 1421.0 nm, 0.261 to 0.698, and -31.4 to -23.8 mV, respectively.

1. Effect of independent factors on PS (P188)

The observed PS varied from 462.2 to 1421.0 nm across different formulation batches, whereas the predicted values ranged from 547.29 to 1439.55 nm (Suppl. material 1: table S4). According to polynomial equation (2), the PS data fit a quadratic model with an F-value of 22.13, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.0001$). A p-value less than 0.0500 confirmed the model's significance, and the lack-of-fit F-value (1.97) indicated an insignificant lack of fit. The predicted and adjusted R^2 values for PS were in good agreement, and the adequate precision of 18.5407 indicated a strong signal, demonstrating that the model could reliably navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of PS responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using P188 is summarized in Table 7.

$$\text{PS (Y}_1\text{)} = + 962.23 - 11.27A + 50.28B + 67.80C - 41.26D - 166.65AB + 316.95AC + 19.60AD + 237.78BC - 48.40BD - 166.57CD - 173.08A^2 - 36.21B^2 + 157.67C^2 - 58.24D^2 \quad (2)$$

Description:

A = P188 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed; AB = P188 concentration \times number of milling balls; AC = P188 concentration \times milling time; AD = P188 concentration \times milling speed; BC = number of milling balls \times milling time; BD = number of milling balls \times milling speed; CD = milling time \times milling speed; A^2 = P188 concentration²; B^2 = number of milling balls²; C^2 = milling time²; D^2 = milling speed².

In polynomial equation (2), the model illustrates the intercept (+962.23), linear effects (A, B, C, and D), interaction effects (AB, AC, AD, BC, BD, and CD), and quadratic effects (A^2 , B^2 , C^2 , and D^2). The negative coefficient for variable A indicates a decrease in PS with increasing P188 concentration, whereas the positive coefficients for B and C suggest an increase in PS with a higher number of milling balls and longer milling time, respectively. Similarly, the negative coefficient for D indicates that PS decreases as milling speed increases. An increase in stabilizer concentration promotes more effective coating of dispersed nanoparticles, enhancing stabilization by reducing interfacial tension (Nielloud et al. 2000). The effects of changes in the independent variables on PS are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S4.

2. Effect of independent factors on PDI (P188)

PDI is a crucial parameter defining the physical stability of nanosuspensions. A low PDI (<0.5) indicates a narrow particle size distribution, which is essential for long-term stability (KianvashRad et al. 2019). PDI values of the developed formulations ranged from 0.261 to 0.698, whereas the predicted values ranged from 0.2410 to 0.7174 (Suppl. material 1: table S4). According to polynomial equation (3), the PDI data fit a two-factor interaction (2FI) model with an F-value of 10.65, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.0001$). A p-value less than 0.0500 confirmed the model's significance, while the lack-of-fit F-value (0.62) indicated an insignificant lack of fit. The predicted and adjusted R^2 values

Table 7. Statistical analysis of responses Y_1 , Y_2 , and Y_3 for the optimal model using P188.

Output analysis model response	Response			Requirement
	Particle size (Y_1)	Polydispersity index (Y_2)	Zeta potential (Y_3)	
Fitting model (F-value)	Quadratic Significant (22.13)	2FI Significant (10.65)	2FI Significant (41.25)	Must be significant
Lack of fit (F-value)	Not significant (1.97)	Not significant (0.62)	Not significant (1.61)	Must not be significant
R^2	0.9538	0.8487	0.9560	
Adjusted R^2 – Predicted R^2	$0.9107 - 0.7744 = 0.1363$	$0.7690 - 0.6576 = 0.1114$	$0.9328 - 0.8755 = 0.0573$	Reasonable agreement; the difference is < 0.2
Adequate precision	18.5407	16.5411	24.2525	> 4
SD	68.06	0.0476	0.4857	
Mean	918.29	0.4785	-27.72	
%CV	7.41	9.94	1.75	
VIF	1.00	1.00	1.00	< 10

VIF = variance inflation factor;

P-values < 0.0500 indicate that model terms are significant.

for PDI were in reasonable agreement, differing by less than 0.2. Furthermore, the adequate precision value of 16.5411 indicated a strong signal, confirming that the model could be used to navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of PDI responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using P188 is summarized in Table 7.

$$\text{PDI } (Y_2) = + 0.4785 + 0.0111A + 0.0044B - 0.0787C + 0.0007D + 0.0160AB - 0.1057AC - 0.0240AD - 0.0397BC - 0.0470BD - 0.1595CD \quad (3)$$

Description:

A = P188 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed; AB = P188 concentration × number of milling balls; AC = P188 concentration × milling time; AD = P188 concentration × milling speed; BC = number of milling balls × milling time; BD = number of milling balls × milling speed; CD = milling time × milling speed.

In polynomial equation (3), the model illustrates the intercept (+0.4785), linear effects (A, B, C, and D), and interaction effects (AB, AC, AD, BC, BD, and CD). The positive coefficients for A, B, and D indicate that PDI increases with higher P188 concentration, a greater number of milling balls, and increased milling speed, whereas the negative coefficient for C reflects a decrease in PDI with longer milling time. The effects of changes in the independent variables on PDI are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S5.

3. Effect of independent factors on ZP (P188)

The zeta potential (ZP) of the different batches of NCC suspensions ranged from −31.4 to −23.8 mV, whereas the predicted values were between −31.26 and −24.12 mV (Suppl. material 1: table S4). According to polynomial equation (4), the ZP data fit a two-factor interaction (2FI) model with an F-value of 41.25, indicating that the model was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). The lack-of-fit F-value of 1.61 indicated that the lack of fit was insignificant. The predicted and adjusted R^2 values for the surface charge were in reasonable agreement, differing by less than 0.2. Furthermore, the adequate precision value of 24.2525 indicated a strong signal, confirming that the model could be used to navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of ZP responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using P188 is summarized in Table 7.

$$\text{ZP } (Y_3) = - 27.72 + 0.0417A - 0.0333B + 0.0917C - 0.5333D - 3.52AB - 0.1750AC - 2.08AD + 1.82BC + 1.15BD - 1.42CD \quad (4)$$

Description:

A = P188 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed; AB = P188 concentration × number of milling balls; AC = P188 concentration × milling time; AD = P188 concentration × milling speed; BC = number of milling balls × milling time; BD

= number of milling balls × milling speed; CD = milling time × milling speed.

In polynomial equation (4), the model illustrates the intercept (−27.72), linear effects (A, B, C, and D), and interaction effects (AB, AC, AD, BC, BD, and CD). The positive coefficients for variables A and C indicate that increasing the concentration of P188 and prolonging milling time have a positive effect on surface charge. In contrast, the negative coefficients for B and D demonstrate that increasing the number of milling balls and milling speed decreases the surface charge. The effects of changes in the independent variables on ZP are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S6.

Optimization of NCC suspension using P407 by BBD

The results of NCC suspension formulation optimization using P407 as a stabilizer, along with both the experimental (actual) and software-predicted responses, are presented in Suppl. material 1: table S5. Based on the experimental data, the PS, PDI, and ZP ranged from 597.4 to 1161.0 nm, 0.562 to 0.808, and −25.9 to −21.1 mV, respectively.

1. Effect of independent factors on PS (P407)

The observed PS values varied from 597.4 to 1161.0 nm across different formulation batches, whereas the predicted values ranged from 736.99 to 1125.95 nm (Suppl. material 1: table S5). According to polynomial equation (5), the PS data fit a linear model with an F-value of 10.58, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.0001$). A p-value less than 0.0500 confirmed the model's significance, while the lack-of-fit F-value (0.4858) indicated that the lack of fit was insignificant. The predicted and adjusted R^2 values for PS were in good agreement, and the adequate precision value of 11.3190 indicated a strong signal, confirming that the model could reliably navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of PS responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using P407 is summarized in Table 8.

$$\text{PS } (Y_1) = + 931.47 - 131.78A + 62.71B - 22.01C - 56.63D \quad (5)$$

Description :

A = P407 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed.

In polynomial equation (5), the model illustrates the intercept (+931.47) and linear effects (A, B, C, and D). The negative coefficient for variable A suggests that increasing the concentration of P407 significantly reduces PS, highlighting the effectiveness of P407 as a stabilizer. Conversely, the positive coefficient for variable B indicates that increasing the number of milling balls tends to increase PS, possibly due to excessive collisions leading to partial particle aggregation. Variables C and D have negative coefficients, implying that longer milling time and higher milling speed contribute to smaller PS through more

Table 8. Statistical analysis of responses Y_1 , Y_2 , and Y_3 for the optimal model using P407.

Output analysis model response	Response			Requirement
	Particle size (Y1)	Polydispersity index (Y2)	Zeta potential (Y3)	
Fitting model (F-value)	Linear Significant (10.58)	Linear Significant (7.07)	Linear Significant (38.95)	Must be significant
Lack of fit (F-value)	Not significant (0.4858)	Not significant (0.60)	Not significant (0.9983)	Must not be significant
R ²	0.6286	0.5307	0.8617	
Adjusted R ² – Predicted R ²	0.5692 – 0.5059 = 0.0633	0.4556 – 0.3468 = 0.1088	0.8396 – 0.7984 = 0.0412	Reasonable agreement; the difference is < 0.2
Adequate precision	11.3190	9.3084	21.6789	> 4
SD	84.17	0.0494	0.4677	
Mean	931.47	0.6616	-23.76	
%CV	9.04	7.46	1.97	
VIF	1.00	1.00	1.00	< 10

VIF = variance inflation factor;

P-values < 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant.

efficient fragmentation. Overall, this model demonstrates that an appropriate stabilizer concentration combined with optimized milling parameters can yield the desired nanometric PS. The effects of changes in the independent variables on PS are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S7.

2. Effect of independent factors on PDI (P407)

PDI values of the developed formulations ranged from 0.5626 to 0.8083, whereas the predicted values ranged from 0.5678 to 0.7554 (Suppl. material 1: table S5). According to polynomial equation (6), the PDI data fit a linear model with an F-value of 7.07, indicating statistical significance ($p = 0.0006$). A p-value less than 0.0500 confirmed the model's significance, while the lack-of-fit F-value (0.60) indicated that the lack of fit was insignificant. The predicted and adjusted R² values for PDI were in reasonable agreement, differing by less than 0.2. Furthermore, the adequate precision value of 9.3084 indicated a strong signal, demonstrating that the model could be used to navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of PDI responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using P407 is summarized in Table 8.

$$\text{PDI } (Y_2) = + 0.6616 - 0.0634A + 0.0081B - 0.0304C - 0.0271D \quad (6)$$

Description:

A = P407 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed.

In polynomial equation (6), the model illustrates the intercept (+0.6616) and linear effects (A, B, C, and D). The negative coefficient for A indicates that increasing P407 concentration significantly reduces PDI, meaning the particles become more uniformly distributed. This supports the role of P407 in stabilizing nanosuspensions by forming a protective layer around nanoparticles, thereby preventing aggregation. The small positive coefficient for B shows that an increase in the number of milling balls slightly increases PDI, suggesting that excessive collisions during milling may cause variation in particle sizes. The negative coefficients of C and D imply that increasing milling time and speed helps reduce PDI by breaking down aggregates

more efficiently, resulting in a more uniform particle size distribution. Overall, this model indicates that an optimal concentration of P407, along with appropriate milling time and speed, can produce a nanosuspension with a narrow and stable particle size distribution. The effects of changes in the independent variables on PDI are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S8.

3. Effect of independent factors on ZP (P407)

The ZP of the different batches of NCC suspensions ranged from -25.96 to -21.1 mV, whereas the predicted values were between -25.83 and -21.69 mV (Suppl. material 1: table S5). According to polynomial equation (7), the ZP data fit a linear model with an F-value of 38.95, indicating that the model was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). The lack-of-fit F-value of 0.9983 indicated that the lack of fit was insignificant. The predicted and adjusted R² values for the surface charge were in reasonable agreement, differing by less than 0.2. Furthermore, the adequate precision value of 21.6789 indicated a strong signal, confirming that the model could be used to navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of ZP responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using P407 is summarized in Table 8.

$$\text{ZP } (Y_3) = - 23.76 + 1.49A - 0.5778B - 0.4472C + 0.2833D \quad (7)$$

Description:

A = P407 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed.

In polynomial equation (7), the model illustrates the intercept (-23.76) and linear effects (A, B, C, and D). The positive coefficient for variable A indicates that increasing the concentration of P407 leads to an increase in ZP, suggesting enhanced electrostatic stability due to greater repulsive forces between particles. In contrast, the negative coefficients for B and C imply that increasing the number of milling balls and prolonging milling time decreases ZP, possibly because the higher mechanical energy interferes with stabilizer adsorption on particle surfaces, thereby reducing electrostatic stability. Meanwhile, the positive coefficient for D indicates that increasing milling speed can improve ZP, likely due to more effective dispersion and

stabilizer coating of the particles. Therefore, the optimal combination of stabilizer concentration, number of milling balls, milling time, and speed is crucial for producing a physically stable nanosuspension. The effects of changes in the independent variables on ZP are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S9.

Optimization of NCC suspension using T80 by BBD

The results of NCC suspension formulation optimization using T80 as a stabilizer, along with both the experimental (actual) and software-predicted responses, are presented in Suppl. material 1: table S6. Based on the experimental results, the PS, PDI, and ZP ranged from 341.1 to 514.3 nm, 0.465 to 0.657, and -29.6 to -13.9 mV, respectively.

1. Effect of independent factors on PS (T80)

The observed PS values varied from 341.1 to 514.3 nm across different formulation batches, whereas the predicted values ranged from 372.33 to 512.37 nm (Suppl. material 1: table S6). According to polynomial equation (8), the PS data fit a linear model with an F-value of 23.38, indicating that the model was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). The lack-of-fit F-value (0.5348) indicated that the lack of fit was insignificant. The predicted and adjusted R^2 values for PS were in reasonable agreement, and the adequate precision of 16.1446 indicated a strong signal, confirming that the model could reliably navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of PS responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using T80 is summarized in Table 9.

$$PS (Y_1) = + 442.35 - 27.56A - 18.13B - 42.46C + 25.04D \quad (8)$$

Description:

A = T80 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed.

In polynomial equation (8), the model illustrates the intercept (+442.35) and linear effects (A, B, C, and D). The negative coefficients for A, B, and C indicate that increasing these parameters reduces PS, while the positive coefficient for D suggests that increasing milling speed increases PS. Therefore, to achieve smaller particle

sizes in formulations using T80 as the stabilizer, higher concentrations of T80, more milling balls, and longer milling times should be applied, while maintaining a moderate milling speed. The effects of changes in the independent variables on PS are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S10.

2. Effect of independent factors on PDI (T80)

The PDI values of the developed formulations ranged from 0.465 to 0.657, whereas the predicted values ranged from 0.4945 to 0.6538 (Suppl. material 1: table S6). According to polynomial equation (9), the PDI data fit a quadratic model with an F-value of 18.15, indicating that the model was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). The lack-of-fit F-value (0.8511) indicated that the lack of fit was insignificant. The predicted and adjusted R^2 values for PDI were in reasonable agreement, differing by less than 0.2. Furthermore, the adequate precision value of 12.6533 indicated a strong signal, confirming that the model could be used to navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of PDI responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using T80 is summarized in Table 9.

$$PDI (Y_2) = + 0.4945 - 0.0007A - 0.0132B - 0.0208C + 0.0163D - 0.0075AB + 0.0035AC + 0.0342AD + 0.0145BC - 0.0447BD - 0.0405CD + 0.0553A^2 + 0.0693B^2 + 0.0334C^2 + 0.0157D^2 \quad (9)$$

Description:

A = T80 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed; AB = T80 concentration \times number of milling balls; AC = T80 concentration \times milling time; AD = T80 concentration \times milling speed; BC = number of milling balls \times milling time; BD = number of milling balls \times milling speed; CD = milling time \times milling speed; A^2 = T80 concentration²; B^2 = number of milling balls²; C^2 = milling time²; D^2 = milling speed².

In polynomial equation (9), the model illustrates the intercept (+0.4945), linear effects (A, B, C, and D), interaction effects (AB, AC, AD, BC, BD, and CD), and quadratic effects (A^2 , B^2 , C^2 , and D^2). In general, increases in B and C tend to decrease PDI (negative coefficients), indicating improved uniformity in particle size distribution. Conversely, an increase in D increases PDI (positive coefficient), suggesting a broader or less

Table 9. Statistical analysis of responses Y_1 , Y_2 , and Y_3 for the optimal model using T80.

Output analysis model response	Response			Requirement
	Particle size (Y1)	Polydispersity index (Y2)	Zeta potential (Y3)	
Fitting model (F-value)	Linear Significant (23.38)	Quadratic Significant (18.15)	Quadratic Significant (33.74)	Must be significant
Lack of fit (F-value)	Not significant (0.5348)	Not significant (0.8511)	Not significant (3.73)	Must not be significant
R^2	0.7891	0.9443	0.9683	
Adjusted R^2 - Predicted R^2	0.7553 - 0.7093 = 0.0460	0.8922 - 0.7680 = 0.1242	0.9387 - 0.8337 = 0.1050	Reasonable agreement, the difference is < 0.2
Adequate precision	16.1446	12.6533	21.6426	> 4
SD	21.25	0.0178	0.9601	
Mean	442.35	0.5640	-18.89	
%CV	4.80	3.16	5.08	
VIF	1.00	1.00	1.00	< 10

uniform particle size distribution. The influence of A is relatively minor (-0.0007), indicating that T80 concentration alone only slightly reduces PDI. However, when combined with other factors, interactions and nonlinear effects may amplify its impact on suspension stability. The effects of changes in the independent variables on PDI are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S11.

3. Effect of independent factors on ZP (T80)

The ZP of the different batches of NCC suspensions ranged from -29.6 to -13.9 mV, whereas the predicted values ranged from -28.78 to -14.08 mV (Suppl. material 1: table S6). According to polynomial equation (10), the ZP data fit a quadratic model with an F-value of 32.74, indicating that the model was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). The lack-of-fit F-value (3.73) indicated that the lack of fit was insignificant. The predicted and adjusted R^2 values for ZP were in reasonable agreement, differing by less than 0.2. Furthermore, the adequate precision value of 21.6426 indicated a strong signal, confirming that the model could be used to navigate the design space. The statistical analysis of ZP responses for the optimized NCC suspension formulation using T80 is summarized in Table 9.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ZP} (Y_3) = & -17.07 + 4.81A - 1.57B + 0.5375C \\ & - 0.4358D + 1.20AB + 0.9750AC + 1.40AD \\ & - 0.3700BC - 0.9250BD + 0.8175CD - 3.31A^2 \\ & - 0.8221B^2 - 0.9383C^2 + 0.5217D^2 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Description:

A = T80 concentration; B = number of milling balls; C = milling time; D = milling speed; AB = T80 concentration \times number of milling balls; AC = T80 concentration \times milling time; AD = T80 concentration \times milling speed; BC = number of milling balls \times milling time; BD = number of milling balls \times milling speed; CD = milling time \times milling speed; A^2 = T80 concentration²; B^2 = number of milling balls²; C^2 = milling time²; D^2 = milling speed².

In polynomial equation (10), the model illustrates the intercept (-17.07), linear effects (A, B, C, and D), interaction effects (AB, AC, AD, BC, BD, and CD), and quadratic effects (A^2 , B^2 , C^2 , and D^2). The positive coefficient for A indicates that increasing T80 concentration significantly increases ZP, suggesting enhanced electrostatic stability through stronger particle–particle repulsion. However, the negative quadratic term ($A^2 = -3.31$) indicates that excessively high T80 concentrations may reduce ZP, emphasizing the need for concentration optimization. The negative coefficient for B (-1.57) implies that increasing the number of milling balls decreases ZP, likely due to excessive collisions interfering with stabilizer adsorption. The small positive effect of C ($+0.5375$) and the slight negative effect of D (-0.4358) indicate that both milling time and speed modestly influence surface charge. Therefore, an optimal balance among stabilizer concentration, number of milling balls, milling time, and speed is critical to achieving a physically stable nanosuspension. The effects

of changes in the independent variables on ZP are illustrated in the 3D surface plot in Suppl. material 1: fig. S12.

In the NCC suspension using P188 as a stabilizer, PS is influenced by all variables—not only the concentration of P188 but also the number of milling balls, milling time, and milling speed. The reduction in PDI (indicating improved homogeneity) is affected by the interactions between P188 concentration and milling time, as well as between milling time and milling speed. The reduction in ZP (reflecting better electrostatic stability) is primarily influenced by milling speed, along with the interactions between P188 concentration and milling speed and between P188 concentration and the number of milling balls. In contrast, in the NCC suspension with P407 as a stabilizer, the decrease in PS (<1000 nm) is mainly driven by increasing P407 concentration. The reduction in PDI is influenced by decreasing P407 concentration, as well as longer milling time and higher milling speed. The reduction in ZP (indicating enhanced electrostatic stability) is predominantly affected by increased P407 concentration. Meanwhile, for the NCC suspension using T80 as a stabilizer, the reduction in PS (<1000 nm) is influenced by lower T80 concentration, the number of milling balls, and milling time, while higher milling speed tends to increase PS. The PDI is affected by both interaction terms and the quadratic forms of all variables. Likewise, ZP is influenced by complex interactions and quadratic effects of all variables, indicating the need for further optimization—such as combining T80 with a poloxamer (P188) (Kutuk 2016; Witika et al. 2020, 2021; Guo et al. 2021).

The results of the BBD analysis demonstrate an inverse relationship between stabilizer concentration and milling speed with the number of milling balls and milling time in relation to PS, which also affects PDI and ZP values. Most of the 3D surface response plots indicate that smaller PS values are achieved when either stabilizer concentration or milling speed is high while the number of balls or milling time is kept minimal, or conversely, when stabilizer concentration or milling speed is low but the number of balls or milling time is increased. To obtain particles within the desired size range, careful selection of stabilizer concentration, number of milling balls, milling time, and milling speed is essential. This is particularly important because excessive milling duration can lead to particle aggregation, especially when a maximum number of milling balls is used. Both excessive and insufficient numbers of milling balls are suboptimal, resulting in a parabolic (non-linear) relationship between the number of balls and the response parameters. This reinforces that the effect of ball number is not isolated but depends on the context of other interacting variables (Kunjir et al. 2025).

In general, longer milling time is expected to facilitate and enhance comminution due to the increased frequency of collisions between API particles and the milling media (Toziopoulou et al. 2017). However, prolonged milling time is also associated with increased temperatures within the milling chamber, which may promote crystal growth due to a greater tendency for Ostwald ripening to occur in the system (Peltonen 2018). A schematic representation of the possible interactions and mechanisms occurring during the milling process is illustrated in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of possible mechanisms of particle interaction that may occur during wet milling (adapted from (M. Li et al. 2016)).

Formulation optimization

The BBD optimization for the NCC suspension formulation using P188 identified the optimal condition at 0.2% w/v, milled with one ball for 30 min at 300 rpm. The resulting PS remained within the nanometric scale, although close to 1000 nm. The PDI was also within the acceptable limit (<0.5), though nearing the upper threshold. Importantly, the ZP value was <-30 mV, indicating good electrostatic stability. Since higher surface charge reduces nanoparticle agglomeration, the NCC suspension formulation with P188 demonstrates favorable nanosuspension stability and is considered suitable for further development.

In contrast, the optimized NCC suspension formulation using P407 at 1.0% w/v, milled with two balls for 20 min at 300 rpm, also produced nanometric particles, but both the PDI and ZP values were outside acceptable ranges. Therefore, the NCC suspension formulation with P407 is not recommended for continued development.

Meanwhile, the NCC suspension formulation using T80 as a stabilizer showed optimal results at a concentration of 1.0% w/v, milled with three balls for 30 min at 350 rpm. This formulation produced the smallest PS among all three stabilizers, and the PDI value remained within the acceptable range. However, the ZP value fell outside the optimal range, suggesting inadequate stability. The complete summary of the optimal NCC suspension formulations using various stabilizers is presented in Table 10.

The formulation of the NCC suspension was further optimized by combining the optimal formulations using P188 and T80. The combination of P188 and T80 was specifically selected because the NCC suspension formulated with P188 exhibited the most favorable ZP value but a relatively large

PS, whereas the formulation with T80 showed the smallest PS but an unfavorable ZP value. Therefore, a combination of the two stabilizers was necessary to achieve a nanosuspension with small, homogeneous, and stable particles.

The results of the NCC suspension formulation using the P188 and T80 combination—based on the optimal formulations shown in Table 10—are presented in Table 11. Among these, Formula TP1 was selected as the final formulation, in which P188 and T80 were used at concentrations of 0.2% w/v and 1.0% w/v, respectively. Milling was performed using three balls for 30 min at a speed of 350 rpm. This formulation yielded the most optimal PS, PDI, and ZP values, attributed to the synergistic effect of the two stabilizers, which provided more effective steric and interfacial stabilization compared with their individual use (Rawlins and Kayes 1980). The DLS results for PS, PDI, and ZP of the optimal GLI–MET NCC suspension formulation (TP1) are presented in Suppl. material 1: fig. S13.

Stability studies

The stability studies were conducted to evaluate the thermal stability of the optimized GLI–MET NCC suspension formulated with a dual stabilizer. Evaluations were performed monthly over a period of three months, focusing on PS as the main parameter, along with PDI and ZP. The suspensions were stored under two conditions: room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) and extreme conditions (40 ± 2 °C). The results of the PS, PDI, and ZP assessments are presented in Table 12 and were compared with the NCC suspension prepared using single stabilizers and without stabilizers. The GLI–MET NCC suspension formulated with the dual stabilizer demonstrated the best stability across all parameters. Furthermore, the results indicate that the NCC suspension was more stable when stored at room temperature than at 40 °C.

The results of the stability test confirm that the combination of P188 and T80 in nanosuspensions enhances both stability and key performance metrics such as PS, PDI, and ZP. This synergistic effect arises from the dual mechanisms of steric and interface stabilization provided by these stabilizers, which are more effective when used together than individually. P188 and T80 contribute both steric

Table 10. Physical parameters of optimized NCC suspensions using various stabilizers.

Type of stabilizer	Physical parameter of optimized NCC suspension				Result of evaluation		
	Concentration (% w/v)	Number of balls	Milling time (min)	Milling speed (rpm)	PS (nm)	PDI	ZP (mV)
P188	0.2	1	20	300	967.5 ± 13.0	0.413 ± 0.041	-33.73 ± 0.82
P407	1.0	2	20	300	895.2 ± 57.2	0.594 ± 0.032	-24.30 ± 1.51
T80	1.0	3	30	350	392.7 ± 14.7	0.458 ± 0.048	-24.57 ± 1.46

Table 11. Result of the combined optimal NCC suspension formulation using P188 and T80.

Formulation code		Physical parameter of optimized NCC suspension				Result of evaluation			
		Concentration (% w/v)		Number of balls	Milling time (min)	Milling speed (rpm)	PS (nm)	PDI	ZP (mV)
		P188	T80						
Variation of P188	PT1	0.2	1	1	20	300	851.6 ± 22.1	0.638 ± 0.014	-34.40 ± 0.78
	PT2	0.4	1	1	20	300	858.5 ± 40.0	0.553 ± 0.058	-30.90 ± 0.14
	PT3	0.6	1	1	20	300	861.7 ± 31.3	0.529 ± 0.071	-31.93 ± 0.49
Variation of T80	TP1	0.2	1	3	30	350	452.6 ± 7.8	0.482 ± 0.012	-31.30 ± 0.26
	TP2	0.2	2	3	30	350	389.9 ± 16.9	0.495 ± 0.015	-27.53 ± 0.87
	TP3	0.2	3	3	30	350	411.8 ± 6.0	0.529 ± 0.036	-24.83 ± 0.42

Table 12. The stability study of the NCC suspension in PS, PDI, and ZP over 3 months.

Sample of NCC suspension	30 days			60 days			90 days		
	PS (nm)	PDI	ZP (mV)	PS (nm)	PDI	ZP (mV)	PS (nm)	PDI	ZP (mV)
Room temperature (25 ± 2 °C, 60% ± 5%)									
P188	765.3	0.564	−39.1	1076	0.575	−38.2	1387	0.586	−37.3
T80	307.1	0.454	−24.1	314.2	0.465	−22.3	321.3	0.476	−20.3
P188+T80	420.5	0.373	−39.6	440.7	0.383	38.7	480.9	0.394	−37.8
Non-stabilizer	1370	0.531	−45.0	1480	0.542	44.1	1590	0.553	−43.2
Accelerated conditions (40 ± 2 °C, 75% ± 5%)									
P188	1153	1.000	−35.7	2131	1.000	−34.8	3142	1.000	−33.9
T80	870	0.329	−12.01	1360	0.337	−10.02	1450	0.348	−8.03
P188+T80	550.3	0.461	−31.4	761	0.572	−22.5	972	0.681	−16.5
Non-stabilizer	2,018×10 ⁴	1.000	−44.2	2,419×10 ⁴	1.000	−43.3	2,820×10 ⁴	1.000	−42.4

hindrance and electrostatic repulsion, which are critical in preventing nanoparticle aggregation (Shete et al. 2014; Yang et al. 2018). This combination results in a more stable nanosuspension by minimizing the risk of Ostwald ripening and aggregation, common challenges in nanocrystal formulations (Shete et al. 2014). Nanosuspensions containing both stabilizers exhibit smaller PS and lower PDI values, indicating a more uniform particle distribution, which is vital for consistent drug delivery (Goel et al. 2025). Additionally, the ZP values suggest a stable system, as higher absolute values are associated with reduced particle aggregation (Yang et al. 2018). Overall, the improved stability and performance characteristics contribute to enhanced bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs, making this formulation approach highly advantageous for pharmaceutical applications (Bajaj et al. 2012; Zawar and Bari 2018).

Table 12 also shows that the higher ZP values observed in the NCC suspensions without stabilizers are most likely due to the absence of steric protection, resulting in full exposure of particle surface charges. Although such systems may appear electrostatically stable ($ZP > \pm 30$ mV), the lack of steric stabilization makes them physically unstable over time, especially at elevated temperatures. This is further supported by the sharply increasing PS values over time, particularly at 40 °C (reaching > 28,000 nm), indicating that the system is physically unstable. In contrast, the presence of nonionic surfactants such as P188 and T80 reduces ZP values due to surface masking effects while still maintaining colloidal stability through steric hindrance (Müller et al. 2002; Honary and Zahir 2013).

The results of the stability study indicate that the increase in PS of the NCC suspension with dual stabilizers (P188 + T80) at 40 °C is most likely due to surfactant desorption caused by thermal stress. This leads to reduced surface stabilization of the particles, enhanced interparticle interactions, and consequently, aggregation. This is supported by the decrease in ZP from −31.4 mV to −16.5 mV, indicating a reduction in surface charge and diminished electrostatic repulsion between particles. Although Ostwald ripening may also occur as a minor mechanism, surfactant desorption is suspected to be the primary cause of particle aggregation. Therefore, further optimization is necessary, particularly for the NCC suspension with dual stabilizers, using a Box–Behnken Design (DoE) approach as part of the synthesis process of GLI–MET NCC powder as a potential oral antidiabetic drug candidate.

Conclusion

The formulation optimization based on the Quality by Design (QbD) approach for the synthesis of GLI–MET NCC suspension using a top-down wet milling method was successfully achieved. A Box–Behnken Design (BBD) was effectively utilized to determine the optimal NCC suspension formulation using various stabilizers. The GLI–MET NCC suspension formulated with a dual stabilizer combination of P188 and T80, at concentrations of 0.2% w/v and 1.0% w/v, respectively, was identified as the most optimal, originating from dried CC produced via the solvent evaporation (SE) technique. This formulation was milled using three balls for 30 min at a speed of 350 rpm. The dual stabilizer combination of P188 and T80 significantly improved the stability and performance metrics of the GLI–MET NCC suspension, resulting in a particle size of 452.6 ± 7.8 nm, a polydispersity index of 0.482 ± 0.012 , and a zeta potential of -31.30 ± 0.26 mV. The formulation also demonstrated good stability over a storage period of 3 months at room temperature.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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References

- Almarsson Ö, Zaworotko MJ (2004) Crystal engineering of the composition of pharmaceutical phases. Do pharmaceutical co-crystals represent a new path to improved medicines? *Chemical Communications* 17: 1889–1896. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b402150a>
- Ammar HO, Salama HA, Ghorab M, Mahmoud AA (2006) Formulation and biological evaluation of glimepiride-cyclodextrin-polymer systems. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 309(1–2): 129–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2005.11.024>
- Bajaj A, Rao MRP, Pardeshi A, Sali D (2012) Nanocrystallization by evaporative antisolvent technique for solubility and bioavailability enhancement of telmisartan. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 13(4): 1331–1340. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-012-9860-x>
- Bian X, Jiang L, Gan Z, Guan X, Zhang L, Cai L, Hu X (2019) A glimepiride-metformin multidrug crystal: Synthesis, crystal structure analysis, and physicochemical properties. *Molecules* 24(20): 3786. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24203786>
- Brosh T, Kalman H, Levy A, Peyron I, Ricard F (2014) DEM-CFD simulation of particle comminution in jet-mill. *Powder Technology* 257: 104–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2014.02.043>
- Censi R, Di Martino P (2015) Polymorph impact on the bioavailability and stability of poorly soluble drugs. *Molecules* 20(10): 18759–18776. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules201018759>
- Cerdeira AM, Mazzotti M, Gander B (2010) Miconazole nanosuspensions: Influence of formulation variables on particle size reduction and physical stability. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 396(1–2): 210–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2010.06.020>
- Chandra A, Kumar Soni R, Sharma U, Jain SK (2013) Nanosuspension: an overview. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics* 3(6): 162–167. <https://doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v3i6.677>
- Chen Z, Higashi K, Ueda K, Moribe K (2022) Transition from amorphous cyclosporin a nanoparticles to size-reduced stable nanocrystals in a poloxamer 407 solution. *Molecular Pharmaceutics* 19(1): 188–199. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.1c00721>
- Childs SL, Chyall LJ, Dunlap JT, Smolenskaya VN, Stahly BC, Stahly GP (2004) Crystal engineering approach to forming cocrystals of amine hydrochlorides with organic acids. Molecular complexes of fluoxetine hydrochloride with benzoic, succinic, and fumaric acids. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 126(41): 13335–13342. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja048114o>
- Darusman F, Fakhri TM, Nurfarida GF (2021) Identification of the Glimepiride and Metformin Hydrochloride Physical Interaction in Binary Systems. *Borneo Journal of Pharmacy* 4(2): 110–116. <https://doi.org/10.33084/bjop.v4i2.1826>
- De Smet L, Saerens L, De Beer T, Carleer R, Adriaensens P, Van Bocxlaer J, Vervaeke C, Remon JP (2014) Formulation of itraconazole nanocrystals and evaluation of their bioavailability in dogs. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics* 87(1): 107–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2013.12.016>
- De Waard H, Frijlink HW, Hinrichs WLJ (2011) Bottom-up preparation techniques for nanocrystals of lipophilic drugs. *Pharmaceutical Research* 28(5): 1220–1223. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-010-0323-3>
- Dewi MK, Muhaimin M, Joni IM, Hermanto F, Chaerunisaa AY (2024) Fabrication of phytosome with enhanced activity of sonneratia alba: formulation modeling and in vivo antimalarial study. *International Journal of Nanomedicine* 19: 9411–9435. <https://doi.org/10.2147/ijn.s467811>
- Ebnesajjad S (2011) Surface and material characterization techniques. *Handbook of Adhesives and Surface Preparation: Technology, Applications and Manufacturing*, 31–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-4377-4461-3.10004-5>
- Giron D (2001) Investigations of polymorphism and pseudo-polymorphism in pharmaceuticals by combined thermoanalytical techniques. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*: 64(1): 37–60. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1011572610005/metrics>
- Goel S, Agarwal V, Sachdeva M (2025) Development of stabilized and aqueous dissolvable nanosuspension encompassing BCS class IV drug via optimization of process and formulation variables. *Recent*

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Fitrianti Darusman: Writing—original draft, visualization, methodology, investigation, data curation, conceptualization. Iyan Sopyan: Writing—review and editing, visualization, validation, conceptualization, resources, supervision. Taofik Rusdiana: Writing—review and editing, conceptualization, resources, supervision.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

- Patents on Nanotechnology 20(1): 61–77. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0118722105317594241025052905>
- Guo M, Sun X, Chen J, Cai T (2021) Pharmaceutical cocrystals: A review of preparations, physicochemical properties and applications. In: *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B* 11(8): 2537–2564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsb.2021.03.030>
- Guzman-Vilca WC, Carrillo-Larco RM (2024) Number of people with type 2 diabetes mellitus in 2035 and 2050: A modelling study in 188 countries. *Current Diabetes Reviews* 21(1): e120124225603. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0115733998274323231230131843>
- Hanum TI, Nasution A, Sumaiyah S, Bangun H (2023) Physical stability and dissolution of ketoprofen nanosuspension formulation: Polyvinylpyrrolidone and Tween 80 as stabilizers. *Pharmacia* 70(1): 209–215. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.70.e96593>
- Hariharan M, Rajan SS, Srinivasan R (1989) Structure of metformin hydrochloride. *Urn:Issn:0108-2701* 45(6): 911–913. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0108270188014246>
- Hinrichsen B, Dinnebir RE (2013) The meaning of preferred orientation in powder diffraction. *Z. Kristallogr* 228(2–3)(1): 83–91. <https://doi.org/10.1155/TSM.14-18.431>
- Honary S, Zahir F (2013) Effect of zeta potential on the properties of nano-drug delivery systems-a review (Part 1). *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 12(2): 255–264. <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v12i2.19>
- Hou X, Guan Y, He S, Wu Z, Bai J, Xu J, Wang J, Xu S, Zhu H, Yin Y, Yang X, Shi Y (2023) A novel self-assembled nanoplatfrom based on retrofitting poloxamer 188 for triple-negative breast cancer targeting treatment. *Chemico-Biological Interactions* 384: 110710. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2023.110710>
- Hu G, Ma A, Wang J (2017) Ligand selectivity mechanism and conformational changes in guanine riboswitch by molecular dynamics simulations and free energy calculations. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling* 57(4): 918–928. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.7b00139>
- Huang Y, Li JM, Lai ZH, Wu J, Lu TB, Chen JM (2017) Phenazopyridine-phthalimide nano-cocrystal: Release rate and oral bioavailability enhancement. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 109: 581–586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2017.09.020>
- Huang Z, Staufienbiel S, Bodmeier R (2022) Combination of co-crystal and nanocrystal techniques to improve the solubility and dissolution rate of poorly soluble drugs. *Pharmaceutical Research* 39(5): 949–961. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-022-03243-9>
- Karashima M, Kimoto K, Yamamoto K, Kojima T, Ikeda Y (2016) A novel solubilization technique for poorly soluble drugs through the integration of nanocrystal and cocrystal technologies. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics* 107: 142–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2016.07.006>
- Kontogiannis O, Selianitis D, Perinelli DR, Bonacucina G, Pippa N, Gazouli M, Pispas S (2022) Non-ionic surfactant effects on innate pluronic 188 behavior: Interactions, and physicochemical and biocompatibility studies. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 23(22): 13814. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms232213814/s1>
- Kunjir S, Pathare P, Sharma S, Deoriya J, Natesan S, Malayandi R (2025) Influence of milling parameters on crystal morphology, thermal behavior, and dissolution of mesalamine nanocrystals. *Pharmaceutical Research* 42: 1409–1427. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11095-025-03891-7>
- Kutuk S (2016) Influence of milling parameters on particle size of ulexite material. *Powder Technology* 301: 421–428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2016.06.020>
- Kwade A (1999) Wet comminution in stirred media mills — research and its practical application. *Powder Technology* 105(1–3): 14–20. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910\(99\)00113-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910(99)00113-8)
- Li J, Jin Y, Wang TY, Lü XW, Li YH (2007) Relative bioavailability and bioequivalence of metformin hydrochloride extended-released and immediate-released tablets in healthy Chinese volunteers. *European Journal of Drug Metabolism and Pharmacokinetics* 32(1): 21–28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf03190986/metrics>
- Li M, Azad M, Davé R, Bilgili E (2016) Nanomilling of drugs for bioavailability enhancement: A holistic formulation-process perspective. *Pharmaceutics* 8(2): 17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics8020017>
- Liu J, Sun Y, Cheng M, Liu Q, Liu W, Gao C, Feng J, Jin Y, Tu L (2021) Improving oral bioavailability of luteolin nanocrystals by surface modification of sodium dodecyl sulfate. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 22(3): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-021-02012-y/metrics>
- Maruthur NM, Tseng E, Hutffless S, Wilson L. M, Suarez-Cuervo C, Berger Z, Chu Y, Iyoha E, Segal JB, Bolen S (2016) Diabetes medications as monotherapy or metformin-based combination therapy for type 2 diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 164(11): 740–751. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M15-2650>
- McLain VC (2008) Safety assessment of poloxamers 101, 105, 108, 122, 123, 124, 181, 182, 183, 184, 185, 188, 212, 215, 217, 231, 234, 235, 237, 238, 282, 284, 288, 331, 333, 334, 335, 338, 401, 402, 403, and 407, poloxamer 105 benzoate, and poloxamer 182 dibenzoate as used in cosmetics. *International Journal of Toxicology* 27(Suppl. 2): 93–128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10915810802244595;ctype:string:journal>
- Merisko-Liversidge E, Liversidge GG (2011) Nanosizing for oral and parenteral drug delivery: A perspective on formulating poorly-water soluble compounds using wet media milling technology. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* 63(6): 427–440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2010.12.007>
- Merisko-Liversidge E, Liversidge GG, Cooper ER (2003) Nanosizing: a formulation approach for poorly-water-soluble compounds. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 18(2): 113–120. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0928-0987\(02\)00251-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0928-0987(02)00251-8)
- Merisko-Liversidge E, McGurk SL, Liversidge GG (2004) Insulin nanoparticles: A novel formulation approach for poorly water soluble Zn-insulin. *Pharmaceutical Research* 21(9): 1545–1553. <https://doi.org/10.1023/b:pham.0000041446.14569.E2>
- Müller RH, Radtke M, Wissing SA (2002) Nanostructured lipid matrices for improved microencapsulation of drugs. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 242(1–2): 121–128. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5173\(02\)00180-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5173(02)00180-1)
- Müllertz A, Perrie Y, Rades T (2016) Analytical techniques in the pharmaceutical sciences - National Library of Medicine Institution. Springer Science and Business Media LLC. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-4029-5>
- Nielloud F, Marti Mestres G, Salager J (2000) Pharmaceutical Emulsions and Suspensions. *Pharmaceutical Emulsions and Suspensions*. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780429344688>
- Panda BP, Krishnamoorthy R, Shivashekaregowda NKH, Patnaik S (2018) Influence of poloxamer 188 on design and development of second generation PLGA nanocrystals of metformin hydrochloride. *Nano Biomedicine and Engineering* 10(4): 334–343. <https://doi.org/10.5101/nbe.v10i4.P334-343>
- Paufler P (2012) *Crystal Engineering. A Textbook*. By Gautam R. Desiraju, Jagadese J. Vittal and Arunachalam Ramanan. Singapore: World

- Scientific, 2011 [ISBN-978 981 4366 86 1. Urn-Issn:0021-8898] 45(2): 374–374. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0021889812001938>
- Pawar VK, Singh Y, Meher JG, Gupta S, Chourasia MK (2014) Engineered nanocrystal technology: In-vivo fate, targeting and applications in drug delivery. *Journal of Controlled Release* 183(1): 51–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2014.03.030>
- Peltonen L (2018) Design space and QbD approach for production of drug nanocrystals by wet media milling techniques. *Pharmaceutics* 10(3): 104. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics10030104>
- Pi J, Wang S, Li W, Kebebe D, Zhang Y, Zhang B, Qi D, Guo P, Li N, Liu Z (2019) A nano-cocrystal strategy to improve the dissolution rate and oral bioavailability of baicalein. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 14(2): 154–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajps.2018.04.009>
- Qiao N, Li M, Schlindwein W, Malek N, Davies A, Trappitt G (2011) Pharmaceutical cocrystals: An overview. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 419(1–2): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2011.07.037>
- Rawlins DA, Kayes JB (1980) Steric stabilization of suspensions. *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy* 6(5): 427–440. <https://doi.org/10.3109/03639048009068715>
- Remenar JF, Morissette SL, Peterson ML, Moulton B, MacPhee JM, Guzmán HR, Almarsson Ö (2003) Crystal engineering of novel cocrystals of a triazole drug with 1,4-dicarboxylic acids. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 125(28): 8456–8457. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja035776p>
- Shete G, Punj D, Prajapat H, Jain H (2014) Stabilizers used in nano-crystal based drug delivery systems | Request PDF. *Journal of Excipients and Food Chemicals* 5(4): 184–209.
- Sinha B, Müller RH, Möschwitzer JP (2013) Bottom-up approaches for preparing drug nanocrystals: Formulations and factors affecting particle size. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 453(1): 126–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2013.01.019>
- Thipparaboina R, Kumar D, Chavan RB, Shastri NR (2016) Multidrug co-crystals: towards the development of effective therapeutic hybrids. *Drug Discovery Today* 21(3): 481–490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2016.02.001>
- Toziopoulou F, Malamataris M, Nikolakakis I, Kachrimanis K (2017) Production of aprepitant nanocrystals by wet media milling and subsequent solidification. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 533(2): 324–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2017.02.065>
- Trask AV, Jones W (2005) Crystal engineering of organic cocrystals by the solid-state grinding approach. *Topics in Current Chemistry* 254: 41–70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/B100995>
- Witika BA, Smith VJ, Walker RB (2020) A comparative study of the effect of different stabilizers on the critical quality attributes of self-assembling nano co-crystals. *Pharmaceutics* 12(2): 182. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics12020182>
- Witika BA, Smith VJ, Walker RB (2020) Quality by design optimization of cold sonochemical synthesis of zidovudine-lamivudine nanosuspensions. *Pharmaceutics* 12(4): 367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics12040367>
- Witika BA, Smith VJ, Walker RB (2021) Top-down synthesis of a lamivudine-zidovudine. *Crystals* 11(1): 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst11010033>
- Yang H, Kim H, Jung S, Seo H, Nida SK, Yoo SY, Lee J (2018) Pharmaceutical strategies for stabilizing drug nanocrystals. *Current Pharmaceutical Design* 24(21): 2362–2374. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612824666180515125247>
- Yu M, Zhan X, Yang Z, Huang Y (2021) Measuring the global, regional, and national burden of type 2 diabetes and the attributable risk factors in all 194 countries. *Journal of Diabetes*, 13(8): 613–639. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1753-0407.13159>
- Zawar LR, Bari SB (2018) Preparation, characterization and in vivo assessment of repaglinide nanosuspension for oral bioavailability improvement. *Recent Patents on Drug Delivery & Formulation* 12(3): 162–169. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1872211312666180713105959>
- Zhang GGZ, Law D, Schmitt EA, Qiu Y (2004) Phase transformation considerations during process development and manufacture of solid oral dosage forms. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* 56(3): 371–390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2003.10.009>

Supplementary material 1

Characterization result of GLI-MET cocrystal

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: Text.

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